

Why Brands Fail? Antecedents and Consequences of Brand Hate A Study of Fashion Industry in Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 03, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 04, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Brand Hate, Negative Word of Mouth, Negative Past Experience, Moral Violation, Product, Organization</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7396279</p>	<p><i>This research is applied in terms of objective and descriptive-co relational in terms of method. The research population included universities' students, Pakistan. The sample size was determined to be 357students' of the universities (University of the Punjab, University of Sindh, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Gomal University, University of Loralai, University of Balochistan, Shah Abdul Latif University and SZABIST Islamabad) of pakistan. A standard questionnaire and personally visit and field methods were used to collect data. SPSS is a program that is used to evaluate data using various statistical tests (Demographic Analysis, Correlation Analysis and Regression Analysis). The study's findings indicate that Negative past experience, Negative word of mouth, and Moral violation all have a positive and significant impact on Brand hate. These findings are supported by a variety of statistical tests, including demographic analysis, descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, and regression analysis, which are all carried out using statistical software. This study provides a comprehensive picture to the managers about the factors perceived to be important by the consumer to make and understand the factors those are highly causes of brand hate. So, this study assists the managers in designing their strategies while selling the products.</i></p>

Introduction

Consumer brand relationships have a big influence on business marketing plans and transactional actions. Customers associate various brands with varying emotions. Some consumers are feeling positively, while others are experiencing the opposite (Zarantonello, Romani et al. 2016). The positive human emotions connected to brands have been the subject of numerous studies in the past, while the negative consumer emotions have received less attention. "Brand hate" is the name given to the bad feeling connected with brands (Kucuk 2021). Positive events are remembered by people, while unpleasant ones are remembered even longer due to human psychology. When people have bad experiences, they usually try as hard as they can to share them with others. The act of spreading hatred is referred to as "bad word of mouth" (Hegner, Fetscherin et al. 2017). Since we live in the age of the internet, consumers instantly share their critical opinions with their friends and peers on the internet, which is problematic from an organizational standpoint. The Oxford Dictionary (2018) defines "hate" as "the feeling of an extreme antipathy for someone or something." Depending on how much and how strongly a person is affected, a specific object or incident may be hateful to some people but not to others (Aziz and Rahman 2022). In a same vein, marketing researchers have begun to investigate the possibility of brand haters (Yadav and Chakrabarti 2022). Extreme distaste for a particular brand's goods or services is known as "brand hatred" (Abbasi, Fayyaz et al. 2022). This may be the case for a variety of reasons, including dislike of the product's flavour, feeling duped, disliking of the individuals involved with the brand, and more. Due to this hatred, many consumers completely avoid a brand (Roy, Sharma et al. 2022). In the worst situation, there may be a public outcry that causes a sizable portion of the consumer base to migrate to another brand out of animosity. Understanding and controlling the causes and effects of brand hatred thus becomes a priority for marketers. Voters are seen as consumers in the political market (Husnain, Syed et al. 2022). Furthermore, unfavourable remarks quickly travelled around the world on blogs and social media. It harms an organization's reputation globally in terms of brand perception and sales revenue (NGUYEN 2021). There are even entire websites devoted to brand hatred, and the goal of these websites is to communicate customer complaints and point out brand flaws in order to influence consumer purchasing behaviour (Baig, Rasheed et al. 2021). Basically, consumer bad experiences in the past with a brand are what lead to brand hatred. When a customer has issues with a product's quality or with the services provided (after-sale support, in-store support), and those issues are either not resolved or keep happening, the customer begins to avoid such brands. Hatred results from these terrible experiences becoming stronger negative feelings. When brand hatred develops, customers start criticizing the company and telling other customers about it (Bryson, Atwal et al. 2021). Companies themselves also play a detrimental role in some moral transgressions. There is an example of a company called

"Abercrombie & Fitch" that exclusively sells apparel that fits or looks nice on individuals. The company also stated that it was solely for those who could afford it and was not intended for the underprivileged. The CEO of the Abercrombie & Fitch brand made the declaration (Jabeen, Kaur et al. 2022). Consumers instantly stopped purchasing from the business out of hatred as a result of the CEO's immoral statement, which had a detrimental impact on sales and brand reputation. Consumers are promoted to associate unfavorable words with companies as a result of moral transgressions on the part of the corporation (Rahi, Ishtiaq et al. 2021). This study focuses on consumers' bad past brand experiences, brands' moral failings, how consumers feel about them as consumers, and how it makes consumers talk negatively about brands (Günaydin and Yıldız 2021).

One example of behavior against recognized practices is behavior that violates morals (Zhu, Xu et al. 2020). How can people determine whether behaviour is unethical in daily life? This issue has been on the clinics' attention for a time (Sharma, Jain et al. 2021). Investigating people's ethical judgment can help us understand how societal norms are maintained and approved practices are designed (Joshi and Yadav 2021). Some hypotheses have made an effort to explain moral judgment by using the concepts of excellent thinking. People, in particular, make more remarkable choices regarding the moral behavior of others when they experience force (Bagozzi and Khoshnevis 2022). Nevertheless, there has been discussion regarding moral judgments and the distinct queasy feeling. Additionally, fright causes people to pay close attention to changes that heuristically suggest the existence of illnesses, such as foreign faces, stout people, and older people (Nguyen and Nguyen 2021). People could also feel disturbed when they witness others breaking moral laws. Pollutants and moral wrongdoing can lead to the spread of microorganisms; this realization makes one feel unwell (Pinto and Brandão 2020).

We occasionally find ourselves as individuals in situations that prevent us from growing in daily life. We struggle to improve ourselves, yet fear creeps in and terrifies us instead. Similarly, our pessimistic outlook prevents us from moving forward in our daily lives (Curina, Francioni et al. 2020). Understanding how to overcome negative thoughts might be a big problem while managing them. Things like fatigue, hunger, lack of sleep, and even the common illness can be brought on by pessimism. Negative thoughts have been shown to be a major factor in self-destructive death, just as they have been in other cases of manslaughter and murder (Joshi and Yadav 2021). Who would have thought that having cynicism in your head could affect your life in such a negative way? Because we make our own decisions and are responsible for all of our difficulties in daily life. As we go through life, we adjust to its bad aspects. With that in mind, regulating negative thoughts can be done in a variety of ways (Rodrigues, Brandão et al. 2020). You can approach this from a variety of angles depending on who you are or the kind of person you will be. My preferred method of getting rid of my pessimistic thoughts eventually is to cause a climatic shift. In order to change your current situation, you must also change your surroundings and the people in it (Bryson, Atwal et al. 2021). Our way of thinking can change when we experience a different environment or meet new people. We should tell ourselves, "It will be an outstanding day today," as soon as we start our day. Consistently doing so would help us maintain our inspiration and optimistic outlook. Additionally, thinking in this way offers you a better perspective and motivates you to work harder to achieve your goal (Meyer 2020). Additionally, this helps us move closer to greatness and motivates us to block out unfavourable thoughts. When we reach that point, our optimistic outlook makes us steer clear of those who are hostile (Jabeen, Kaur et al. 2022). A positive outlook encourages us to draw in like-minded people. Positivity makes us see things more clearly and opens us up to better opportunities.

There are a few different ways to overcome unfavorable thoughts and actually witness their eradication. Contrarily, there are occasions when it is best to just write down your problems. When they are recorded, shred the paper into a ball and throw it away. Right now, you've seen all of your negative thoughts actually disappear (Loureiro and Kaufmann 2018). Considering all, life can deal us some pretty harsh blows that occasionally will ruin us. In any case, it is up to us to decide if we require their control and transformation into the people we would prefer to avoid.

Anger can occasionally be turned into a dreadful tool that hurts its owner more than others. It is a common inclination that everyone might experience. However, the challenge is in how to effectively manage it and prevent it from negatively influencing your life (Kashif, Devrani et al. 2021). Outrage is a common emotion, but intense resentment can manifest as ferocity, retaliation, and other undesirable outcomes. Revenge has evolved into a well-known negative method people use nowadays.

People frequently divide or separate themselves, whether consciously or unconsciously. From one angle, being accustomed to parting and separation helps people manage their lives and prevents them from being affected by traumas sustained in adolescence and adulthood, prior experiences, and memories that would otherwise cause them to forget about the unbearable suffering and stress (Jain and Sharma 2019). However, separating or separation may be a very dangerous weapon that weakens people's minds because it limits their perceptions of the present reality, alters the situation they should be facing, and removes them from interpersonal relationships. However, the happy or bad aspects of separation and parting depend on the people involved. People are unaware of their pasts since they didn't view those experiences specifically; therefore they are unaware of how skilled their former lives were (Fahmi and Zaki 2018). The three clothing line brands Gul Ahmad, Nishat Linen, and

Alkaram from the Pakistani consumer market are the focus of this study. Targeted consumers of these three brands will be asked about their opinions and what makes them feel unfavorably about them. This study aids marketing managers of the aforementioned clothing businesses in carefully crafting their marketing strategies to avoid offending their target market and inciting brand aversion. Researchers claim that 95% of companies fail in the start of their existence, and some brands that are quite well-known in the market suddenly have people stop using them. What are the main reasons for it? In addition to investigating the issues and understanding the causes, this study is crucial for the development of fashion-related items.

Literature Review

Brand Hatred

While brand love demonstrates a good and positive interaction between customers and the brand, brand hatred demonstrates a negative emotional connection between the brand and customers (Aziz and Rahman 2022). Brand hatred is associated with the goal to consciously disregard or reject a brand, but it is also associated with consumer behaviour that expresses unfavourable sentiments through boycotting or disliking corporate products (Zhang and Laroche 2020).

Dissatisfaction was evident as unfavourable emotions, such as a positive reaction to a suggested use of experience. Although discontent was a significant trigger for complaining behaviour, dissatisfaction had only been established to account for a tiny subset of complaining behaviour (Fetscherin 2019). Only 20 to 35 percent of those customers had complained to the marketer, according to the response they had given to their most unsatisfactory customer experience. The degree of a person's hatred of a particular brand is referred to as brand hate. The term "brand hate phenomenon" refers to the range of feelings one experiences while in a hostile environment. It includes feelings of embarrassment (Noor, Mansoor et al. 2021), disgust (Rodrigues, Brandão et al. 2020), and distaste. A consumer always tries to denigrate or at least reduce a brand when they feel duped by it and develop hatred for it in themselves (Curina, Francioni et al. 2020). According to Fitness and Fletcher (2019), when interpersonal ties are strong, hate is present but expressed with a relative lack of fervour. Either they abandon the conversation or they just leave. Therefore, we might contend that if consumers have a strong emotional connection to a brand, their level of hatred will be greater if they perceive a change in the brand's behaviour or an ideological shift that doesn't align with their own. Brand Hate refers to the making of disparaging remarks regarding a brand's business activities in public or private. At first, this technique is so little that customers only have negative things to say about it. The strength of hate then increases in accordance with the degree of dissatisfaction, which controls the phenomena of hatred. That was considered a relevant driver of unfavourable word of mouth by earlier researchers (Kucuk 2019). Customers begin disseminating unfavourable information about the brand using all of their influence and resources. In addition to tarnishing the reputation of the brand, they want to make sure that everyone who is already a customer or who might become one will think twice before buying anything from that company. The fundamental goal of their ferocious defamation is to expose individuals responsible for the error and to penalize the brand. Similar to this, when voters dislike a political party, they begin to criticize the party in an effort to discredit it. If a significant number of voters voice this opinion, it might become terribly damaging to the party. However, because a political party is a much larger institution than a single voter, the impact of such defamation relies on the size of the voter group involved in the process (Bayarassou, Becheur et al. 2020).

People purchase products from the market to satisfy their needs and wants. If a customer has a bad experience with a product once, they are less likely to become repeat or loyal customers of a company because they feel bad about the product or neglect the brand as a result of their bad experience. This could be because the product was defective due to its (usage, guarantee, expiry dates) (Kucuk 2019). In terms of the mark the board, consumer hostility and the growth of brand-scorn consumer connections are steadily being researched, and this necessitates businesses to more easily appreciate these wonders. The growing ability of customers to strongly or negatively affect others further supports this inspiration (Cioppi, Curina et al. 2019).

Negative Past Experience

Most of the time, people cut off relationships with unsuccessful people and only introduce their products to successful people (Vania, Rader et al. 2014). For instance, viewers may report a win for their favorite teams as "we won" and a loss as "they lost" (Shields, Trinh et al. 2022). The purpose of those actions appears to be obvious. People look for ways to avoid reflecting failure and to unwind in reflected success. Researchers hypothesized that the attitude's underlying cause was either experiencing administration (Forster, Rogers et al. 2022). Negative rumor spread quickly and may develop into stories that were more detailed than the real world, which was dangerous. The effects are also increased by the ability to spread bad information quickly through modern outlets like the internet (Magis-Weinberg, Gys et al. 2021). Information circulated swiftly, and a single post may go haywire. It might also start a conversation in which diverse unpleasant experiences were discussed inside the same clearly audible conversation (Yu, Lau et al. 2022). Based on previous social interactions, we hypothesized that moral transgression, whether it involves actual pollution or not, will affect how disturbed countenances are prepared. However, both types of moral transgression will stimulate brain activity with different societal characteristics (Abbas 2020). In essence, an encounter is what you make it out to be, and by

looking for the good exercise in each, you may transform the past presentations regarding unpleasant interactions (Hoover, Lockhart et al. 2022). When you experience or reflect on such painful interactions, they are showing you that something is wrong—not with your external environment but rather with yourself. Similar to how physical suffering makes you aware of a problem so you can fix it, mental suffering makes you aware of a psychological problem that has to be fixed (Desmet, Dezutter et al. 2022).

Think about everything. If you had burned yourself as a child by touching a hot stove or oven, the agony you experienced would have taught you never to repeat the mistake. Without the torment, you would have suffered severe injuries (Sanwal and Ullah 2021). Similar to this, the pain in your emotional or passionate world is likely trying to save you from repeating unpleasant experiences or from getting gravely burned in your life (Rodrigues, Zoppolat et al. 2022). Learn to regard all of your perceived unfavourable experiences as a close friend letting you know what's going on or what needs your attention (Danilowska 2022).

Allow any unpleasant, receptive, or passionate energy to pass through you and away, whenever and however it manifests. You can be aware of it, but you shouldn't focus your attention on it or give it any of your energy because it has been programmed to exist outside of you. Your attentiveness and anticipation to provide will cause the situation's or feelings negative energy to transform on its own (NGUYEN 2021). If ever, for unexplained reasons, it is unrealistic to expect to reach higher contemplations and discern the grand scheme at the time, do something different and divert your attention from it to something unrelated that makes you feel calm, tranquil, and joyful. This is a simple technique to prevent responding to the present second involvement in a meaningless way, not an attempt to avoid it (Rahi, Ishtiaq et al. 2021).

H1: Positive and significant relationship between Negative Past Experience and Brand Hate

Negative word of mouth

In terms of marketing, word-of-mouth communication was crucial for providing customers with information about product, the company, and its reputation in marketplace (Talwar, Talwar et al. 2021). Word-of-mouth advertising typically involves customers, who may have previously had positive or negative experiences with the brand and its reputation, both of which may be favourable or unfavourable (Nguyen, Lee et al. 2021). The majority of authors had only studied positive and negative verbal exchange, but both have made reference to it. It is typically discussed in terms of enlightening people about new products (dissemination of advancements) as opposed to customer interchanges about existing products. Finally, persons taking part in bad WOM activities might not actually be leading the way to a conclusion. A study of projects looking at how bad news affects customers (Donthu, Kumar et al. 2021). Direct or indirect expressions of active responses are possible. Direct active actions include retaliatory behaviour and bad WOM, whereas indirect active actions include complaints, such as anti-brand websites and anti-brand actions (Furrer, Kerguignas et al. 2021). According to Grégoire et al. (2009), brand hate results in either a desire for vengeance or a wish to avoid. The former catches "customers' need to distance themselves from any dealings with the firm," while the former refers to "customers' urge to punish and bring harm to firms for the damages they have caused. Additionally, contends that the severity of the consumer's feelings of hatred affects the outcomes of hate. Another interviewee stated, "I felt the actual bigotry against the Muslims when I was there and I had a profound sense of anger" (Female, 35). This encounter caused him to feel hate toward the location. According to (Kucuk 2019) this instance of hate resembles "prejudiced hate" in that the participant is assaulting the target as a result of the prejudice that has been fostered in society. In other words, the object of this form of hatred is not the one who is being despised but the one who is doing the hating. In a unique way, word of mouth contrasted with the mainstream press and media. When a person purposefully posts a poor review or openly promotes unfavourable information, the group of people is forced to believe that information. Any new information quickly becomes more reliable (Casidy, Duhachek et al. 2021). As a result, businesses used surveys, contextual research, and favourable testimonials as sales tools. Any convincing direct evidence fosters confidence and increases the possibility of change (Seo and Jang 2021). Word of mouth is an additional marketing and advertising tool. Therefore, word-of-mouth marketing isn't just for large, international corporations. It's for small, medium, and large businesses that can successfully manage word of mouth (Abbas, Akram et al. 2022). In this essay, I have discussed modern marketing, word of mouth, how word of mouth can still affect marketing, and the benefits and drawbacks of word of mouth. Information is spread orally from person to person through word of mouth (Huang and Philp 2021). In the twenty-first century, word-of-mouth marketing is a viable strategy for medium-sized businesses as well as large ones. In the last few years, marketing research has undergone significant shift. There are notable differences between the marketing influences and approaches of the 1950s and now, including the emergence of innovation, the presence of fierce competition, environmental factors, ethical considerations. Even if historical designs, elements of impacts, and methods changed, we can see that Word of Mouth is still having an impact on marketing now. Word-of-mouth refers to how customers or users talk about your product, service, or event. It might be either beneficial or unfavourable in both methods (Lee and Suh 2020). If people speak highly of you, you will continue to have enormous success; nevertheless, if they do not, you will continue to experience severe difficulties. Numerous businesses disregard customer reviews and put themselves in danger of going out of business. Therefore, it is

essential that every business do its own WOM marketing research study and gauge public opinion of its services and goods (Seo and Jang 2021).

However, negative word of mouth had a negative effect. There was no one term that applied to all customer complaints and the study of complaining attitudes was linked to numerous definitions from various fields of research. The demonstrated and unproven structures were those (Cui, Hu et al. 2018). Negative word-of-mouth viewed as unfavorable publicity coming from a dependable source and is very difficult to manage. According to past research, the manner in which the marketer ends the commercial relationship influences the degree to which a client is inclined to share unfavorable word-of-mouth. Consumers tend to propagate rumors about brands when they have bad experiences with them (Strathern, Ghawi et al. 2022). This happens when consumers have bad experiences with any brand that is available to customers. Word-of-mouth advertising has the ability to instantly improve or damage a product, service, or any organization's reputation. In my introduction, I said that "people love to chat." The only thing we need to do is deliver the correct product at the right time in the right quality and satisfy them if we want positive feedback from them. Earning that excellent discussion and chatter is what Word of Mouth is all about. No matter what you are selling computers, furniture, or jet engines people will undoubtedly consult with others before making a decision (Donthu, Kumar et al. 2021). Customers seek advice from those they trust first, whether they are friends, family, coworkers, etc. Therefore, in order to advertise a product by word of mouth, we need provide consumers with a cause to talk about the items and should make it simple for them to do so (Akram, Khan et al. 2022). Unpleasant word-of-mouth is based on prior poor experiences; if someone had positive past experiences with a product, then their reviews of that brand were positive; conversely, if they had negative past experiences with that product, then their reviews of that brand were negative (Arora, Gupta et al. 2021).

Negative word of mouth occurs when a large number of customers have the same problem with a product or company. When behaving in accordance with moral traits, models, and rules recognized by association's members and society, a person or organization is said to have integrity (Jeong and Yoo 2021). Therefore, it is possible to define integrity infractions as going against these moral principles and standards. A firm had a duty to present a brand in the marketplace in accordance with the customs and values of the local populace (Abbas, Khan et al. 2020). Customers had harsh words for a brand when a company could not offer a brand or defraud them, and they knew it because they wanted the company to offer a brand that upheld their moral principles (Xiao, Hudders et al. 2018).

H2: Positive and significant relationship between Negative Words Mouth and Brand Hate

Moral Violation

Every time a person went over a reasonable limit, an ethical limit, a physical limit, or a concomitant commercial agreement, it was a violation. When a burglar opens your door's lock by picking it that was an invasion of your property. A rude display or the crossing of someone's bodily boundaries is both examples of violations (Khavas, Perkins et al. 2021). Morality is based on a set of guidelines intended to control interpersonal behaviour and permit peaceful coexistence. But there was growing evidence in that area of study that moral judgment was based on instinctive, effortless, and emotional mechanisms (Zhang, Bian et al. 2021). The ability to distinguish between activities that are appropriate or inappropriate depends on a system of moral principles and is crucial for both the person and society (Li, Luo et al. 2021). However, it has been studied in numerous spheres of life how people form moral attitudes and ideals. In light of this, three studies support our beliefs that, unless the violation is related to the offender's work performance, ethical violations are also harmful (Sharma, Jain et al. 2022).

Additionally, people have an avoidance when outlook and the expected results for offender are large, moral violations associated with work performance are more detrimental. In the end, these effects are caused by negative emotions, which encourage effective dissociation while encouraging administrative concentration (Husnain, Wang et al. 2021). This investigation yields a few significant findings. First of all, it acknowledges the administrative centre hypothesis as a crucial motivating premise that can encourage. Second, analysis supports past estimates on profound quality writing, demonstrating that some consumers employ sentiments to judge good violation and are unprepared to separate the outcomes of excellent violation from brand assessments (Gois, Moura et al. 2022). According to Brown and Heimberg (2001) findings in each study, those who wrote about emotionally charged events saw a significant improvement in their physical and mental health. They were more content, less worried, and less sad. They experienced decreased blood pressure, enhanced immunological function, and fewer doctor visits in the months following the writing sessions. Additionally, they reported having more successful relationships, better memories, and at work.

Pennebaker intervention at a Dallas-based computer firm that let go of one hundred senior engineers. Most of these individuals were above 50 and had been employed by the business since they were in college. They were terrified and perplexed after being fired because this was the only work life they had ever known. They had to deal with the possibility of never again working in their line of business. None of them had a new job after four months (O'Mara, Jackson et al. 2011). When engineers were "downsized," Pennebaker and his team wondered if sharing their stories in writing may be of assistance. The engineers agreed to take part because they were eager

to do anything that would improve their work prospects. One group of engineers was asked to write by Pennebaker about being let go. They discussed the stresses this put on their health, marriages, and finances, as well as their intense anxieties about the future (Tepe and Aydinli-Karakulak 2019). They also discussed their sentiments of embarrassment, rejection, and fury. Two control groups either didn't write anything at all or wrote about time management. There were no differences between the groups before the writing process in terms of their motivation or the effort they were putting forth to find a new job (Landmann and Hess 2017). The degree of difference between them, though, was astounding after that. The guys who had written about their true feelings were three times more likely to have found new employment than those who had not, just months after the intense writing sessions. The men's writing not only assisted them in processing their experiences, but also in overcoming their dejected inaction and taking meaningful action. People can declare with certainty that showing up and giving voice to feelings is a really effective method to deal with stress, worry, and grief after many more research have been conducted with many thousands of participants, including youngsters and the elderly, students and professionals, healthy and ill (Pauls, Shuman et al. 2022). (For those who dislike using a pen and paper or a keyboard, writing does not have any special powers. For instance, speaking into a voice recorder can provide the same outcomes.

Others, on the other hand (i.e., individuals with an anticipatory mindset), take outcomes into account when making judgments (Chen 2010). We conclude by discussing the practical implications for businesses and brands.

H3: *Positive and significant relationship between Moral Violation and Brand Hate*

Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

Research design is defined as a procedural outline for every research activity, and there are various categories by classification depending upon degree of structure, data collection method, effect of variable under study, purpose of study, time dimension, topical scope, research environment and participants' perceptions. In this research we will go for cross-sectional research to collect data at a single point of time, because we need response from participants with help of Questionnaires research activity (Cooper, Schindler, & Sun, 2003). In this study I adopt the questionnaires from the previous studies. Number of five (05) for Brand Hate (Zarantonello, Romani et al. 2016), five (05) questions for Negative Past Experience (Hegner, Fetscherin et al. 2017), five (05) questions for Moral Violation (Hegner, Fetscherin et al. 2017) and also five (05) for Negative Word of Mouth (Zarantonello, Romani et al. 2016) on five point Likert scale. Likert-type scale will used as (1= Strongly Disagree; 2= Disagree; 3= Neutral; 4= Agree; 5= Strongly Agree). The population of this study consists of educational sector of Pakistan. Among educational sector only university students were targeted in which we selected the department of Business Administration. Eight (08) universities which are University of the Punjab, University of Sindh, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Gomal University, University of Loralai, University of Balochistan, Shah Abdul Latif University and SZABIST Islamabad were took into consideration. The total Population of these universities were 4650. The sample sizes of this study were 357 university's students. Simple random sampling technique will be used for primary data collection. In this sampling technique respondents have equal chance of selection from the population. Data was collected from the respondents through questionnaire. Questionnaire would be adapted according to variables and keeping in mind about

literature for research purpose. Questionnaire comprised of demographic section including 20 items of Negative past experience, Moral violation, Brand hate and Negative word of mouth. The data will be collected through 5-point likert scale questionnaires which measures the relationship between negative past experience, moral violation, negative word of mouth and brand hate.

Data Analysis and Results

Cronbach's alpha should be better than 0.7, according to Nunnally (1987), for the instrument to be considered reliable. The table showed that all variables have Cronbach's alpha values greater than 0.7, indicating that the instrument is trustworthy (Leech, Barrett et al. 2004, Morgan, Leech et al. 2004). The validity of questionnaire is checked by educational experts.

Demographic Analysis

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	158	44.3	44.3	44.3
Female	199	55.7	55.7	100.0
Total	357	100.0	100.0	

The Data that was collected from different people some are male and some are female. The number of male is 158 and female is 199 and total number of people is 357. The cumulative percentage is from female is 100 and from male is 55.7.

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-23	97	27.2	27.2	27.2
24-29	147	41.2	41.2	68.3
30-35	58	16.2	16.2	84.6
35-Above	55	15.4	15.4	100.0
Total	357	100.0	100.0	

The Data that was collected from different people and people have different age. The age of people range from 18-23 is 97 and the age of people range from 24-29 is 147 and the people range from 30-35 is 58 and the people range from 35-above is 55 the total number of people is 357.

Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Bachelor	86	24.1	24.1	24.1
Master	198	55.5	55.5	79.6
M.Phil	65	18.2	18.2	97.8
Ph.D	8	2.2	2.2	100.0
Total	357	100.0	100.0	

The Data that was collected from different people have different education level. The Bachelor people is 86 and Master people is 198 and M.phil is 65 and the PHD people is 8 the total number of people is 357.

Descriptive statistics

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
MoralViolation	357	4.00	4.80	4.5143	.16264
NegativePE	357	4.20	4.80	4.6073	.13346
NegativeWM	357	4.20	5.00	4.7557	.19986
BrandHate	357	4.40	5.00	4.8387	.23408
Valid N (listwise)	357				

Descriptive statistics explained the trend and level of existence of variables. The minimal and maximal showed the correctness of data and it should be in limits of the measurement scale of instruments. As shown above, the maximal and minimal values are in the range from 1 to 5 Likert scale. No value is less than 1 and no value above then 5 for all the independent and dependent variables. The mean of two variables is greater than 3 that means all the average of responses lies in the agreement are the values of skewness should range from -1 to +1 while kurtosis should range from -3 to +3 and this is acceptable range (Sekaran and Bougie 2003). It is clear that all the statistics of skewness and kurtosis are within the acceptable range. So data collected for this study is normal this is also the first and foremost assumption of regression analysis.

Correlation Analysis

Correlations

	MoralViolation	NegativePE	NegativeWM	BrandHate

MoralViolation	Pearson Correlation	1	.	.	
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	357			
NegativePE	Pearson Correlation	.510**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	357	357		
NegativeWM	Pearson Correlation	.405**	.395**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	357	357	357	
BrandHate	Pearson Correlation	.291**	.271**	.553**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	357	357	357	357

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation shows the relation between the variables. If the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient is between - 0.3 to +0.3 then there exists a weak relationship between the variables. If the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient range is 0.3-0.7 then there exists a moderate relationship. And above 0.7 shows a strong relationship between variables (Leech, Barrett, & Morgan, 2004). Moral Violation, Negative Past Experience and Negative Word of Mouth have a positive effect on Brand Hate.

Regression Analysis

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	NegativeWM, NegativePE, MoralViolation ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: BrandHate

b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.559 ^a	.312	.306	.19497

a. Predictors: (Constant), NegativeWM, NegativePE, MoralViolation

b. Dependent Variable: BrandHate

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.088	3	2.029	53.381	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.419	353	.038		
	Total	19.507	356			

a. Dependent Variable: BrandHate

b. Predictors: (Constant), NegativeWM, NegativePE, MoralViolation

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.273	.387		3.291	.001
	MoralViolation	.094	.076	.065	1.228	.220
	NegativePE	.062	.093	.036	.672	.502
	NegativeWM	.600	.058	.513	10.306	.000

a. Dependent Variable: BrandHate

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	4.4939	5.0241	4.8387	.13077	357
Residual	-.35276	.50615	.00000	.19415	357
Std. Predicted Value	-2.637	1.418	.000	1.000	357
Std. Residual	-1.809	2.596	.000	.996	357

a. Dependent Variable: BrandHate

The regression analysis shows the value of Durbin Watson is in the range. So there is no problem of serial correlation. The R showed multiple correlation coefficients. It is the combined correlation between the independent variable and the dependent variable. R2 is the explanatory power of the model. It depicted the explained variation in the Dependent variable due to the independent variable. The value of R square is that explained variation in the dependent variable due to the independent variable. It explained the variation for the sample and adjusted R square showed the variation for population i.e. four banks in Pakistan. Beta is the slope of relationship. However the significant value of the variable is less than 0.05, so the relationship between the variables is significant so hypotheses are accepted.

Chart

<i>Hypotheses</i>	<i>Stat</i>	<i>Result</i>
Hypothesis (H1)	Positive and significant	Accepted
Hypothesis (H2)	Relationship between	Accepted
Hypothesis (H3)	Negative Past Experience and Brand Hate . Positive and significant relationship	Accepted

Summary

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Conclusion and Recommendations

Managerial Implications

The study provides useful insights knowledge of Brand Hate to managers to design brand for marketing their product. In addition to this study provides a roadmap and an action plan to the manager to rectify the existing problem of decreased demand by marketing their product on a credible way. These managerial consequences are motivated by ethical behaviour, the incorporation of additional consumer inspection for an efficient response, historical relationships, as well as the consumer's proactive approach. This necessitates a proactive and ongoing assessment of the customer connection's nature, as individuals with a higher "relationship quality" may be more likely to retaliate. While hate emotions or feelings are involved and anything changes, either from the brand or the consumer, a brand may experience a distinct set of consequences when attempting to create a relationship with consumers.

Theoretical Implications

The findings of this research have made several contributions to the existing literature. Researchers have tested the association of firm's performance with other variables in other sections in the world (Molino, Cortese et al. 2019). The present study has focused on the association of Negative Past Experience, Negative Word of Mouth, Moral Violation and Brand Hate in Pakistan. In previous research, only few researchers have investigated the Brand Hate and its reaction on organization image.

Research Limitations

The first restriction is the lack of resources and time. The study's main drawback is the absence of any moderation in this investigation. In addition to the aforementioned, a significant flaw in the study is that it does not account for the effects of other variables that affect a organization image, such as brand image, consumer decision-making, and shared geographic location.

Future Research

The first recommendation for the future researcher can replicate the same model in different context. This research has been done in Pakistan. So, future research can take other area of the world in consideration. Secondly, this study is done in the context of only four variables; future research can target other variables (moderator/mediator).

Conclusion

Brand hating was found to be predicted by bad experiences. In fact, a consumer's relationship with a brand might suffer and have a negative effect when they have a bad encounter. Additionally, it has been shown to predict the avoidance of experiential brands. Brand hatred reveals to be a powerful mediator in the context of Negative word of mouth, also having a direct relationship and causing an increase in the outcome. As mentioned by the literature, brand hatred can cause people to complain in public, which is a sort of bad word of mouth. According to this hypothesis, the study shows that bad experiences exclusively predict poor word of mouth when they are mediated by brand-hating emotions. According to reports, brand revenge need not be driven by a bad experience. Brand hate is predicted by symbolic incongruity. Accounting for brand hatred demonstrates that it influences Negative word of mouth, but it also demonstrates that it affects the result directly. In fact, symbolic incongruity has been connected to Negative word of mouth since it connects the consumer's identity to the brand. It only causes bad word of mouth when it is influenced by brand-hating feelings. The expectation that negative word of mouth will be a result of all variables suggests that emotion is crucial in determining its incidence. Whether or not brand hatred is a factor, symbolic incongruity implies that it has an impact on brand retaliation.

Brand revenge is less driven by a bad experience than it is by a symbolic incongruity, although it has always been mediated by brand hatred. The term "brand retribution" refers to a variety of actions consumers take to financially harm a brand, such as complaining, insulting, or attempting to negatively impact the brand as a whole. By concentrating on a single industry, this research demonstrated a novel methodology when compared to prior studies that analyze consumer brands across many industries and to the best of our knowledge in the literature. It also examined how well customers and non-consumers interacted with fresh managerial insights are presented by telecommunication brands. It connects consumer-brand interactions to previously known theoretical frameworks based on interpersonal and psychological research. The methodology used in this study gave a clear picture of how brand hatred related to various outcomes and antecedents. In addition to being applicable to different situations and compared to the ones included in this study, the recommended criteria in the literature have been demonstrated to be reliable in specific contexts within the telecoms industry. The investigation of consumer brand relationships in the service sectors in this context complements earlier studies in brand hatred research that focused primarily on luxury or food service businesses but did not really offer much insight into certain more utilitarian brands. Consequently, it offered insightful information on a sector, service marketing consumers, and service. In three ways, this study adds to the body of knowledge already on the unfavourable relationship between customers and companies. First off, as was already noted, this study fills a gap in the literature by focusing on the study of the good brand-consumer interactions, despite the fact that there is an increasing demand for research on the negative aspects of consumer-brand relationships. Furthermore, this article examines the impact on the telecommunications sector for the first time. Thirdly, it supports other studies that looked at how brand hatred affects Negative word of mouth. This research offers businesses insight into how Negative word of mouth might result from brand animosity, which has practical ramifications for businesses. To combat the phenomenon of brand hatred or, more effectively, to try to reverse or neutralize as much as possible the adverse outcomes from the poor previous experiences of current consumers with the brand, businesses and brands need to develop strong defense mechanisms. However, as pointed out by, any business may please all of its present or potential customers if it can manage the direst circumstances and lessen the harm caused by the most antagonistic customers. The study's conclusions can be utilized to explore further variables in the interaction between a services brand and its customers.

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